

Condensation of Substituted Acetophenones with Methylene Iodide. Part I. Formation of 1,5-Diketones

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Resacetophenone, respropiofenone, resbutyrophenone, and their halogenated derivatives condense with methylene iodide in sodium ethoxide solution, yielding 1,5-diketones. The preparation of several 1,5-diketones has been described.

Chakravarti *et al.*^{1,2} reported the synthesis of isoflavanones by the condensation of 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone with methylene iodide. The present authors in attempting to synthesise chromanones (III) by condensation of substituted resacetophenones and its higher homologues (I) with methylene iodide in the same way, obtained the reaction products as 1,5-diketones (II) and not as chromanones. The molecular weight determination, the formation of 2,4-DNP and tetra-acetyl derivatives, I.R. spectra, and mass spectrograph support the diketonic structure. Further, the oxidation of tetramethyl derivative of (II:R = R' = H) furnishes β -resorecylic acid dimethyl ether.

(I)

(II)

(III)

EXPERIMENTAL

α -*Bis*-2,4-dihydroxybenzoylpropane (II:R=R'=H).—Resacetophenone³ (7.6 g.) was condensed with methylene iodide (13.4 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide (prepared from 3.5g. Na and 40 ml of absolute ethanol). The reaction product, isolated in the usual way,

1. *Science & Culture*, 1961, 27, 407.

2. *Ibid.*, 1962, 28, 242.

3. Robinson and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1494.

crystallised from ethanol as colorless rods, m.p. 201-202°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 64.55; H, 5.06%). The compound is sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetic acid and highly soluble in acetone and chloroform. It develops a violet colour with ferric chloride solution.

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute ethanol as cubic crystals, m.p. 186°. (Found: C, 61.91; H, 5.2. $C_{23}H_{24}O_{10}$ requires C, 62.0; H, 4.9%). Mass spectrophotograph records signals at masses corresponding to loss of acetyl groups as $CH_3-C=O$. Signals at mass 382 and 364 may be explained as follows: $382 = 484 - 60$ (CH_3COOH)— $42(CH_2=C=O)$ and $364 = 484 - 2 \cdot 60$ (CH_3COOH)².

Infrared spectra (Fig. 1) of the above compound in Nujol show λ_{max} at 1750, 1595, 1290, 1260, 1170, 1125, 1055, 920, 895, 825, 815, 718 cm^{-1} .

2,4-DNP of the above diketone crystallised from dioxane-ethanol, m.p. 290°. (Found: N, 16.30. $C_{19}H_{24}O_{12}N_2$ requires N, 16.56%).

The *tetramethyl* derivative, prepared with dimethyl sulphate in acetone solution in presence of K_2CO_3 , crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 67.58; H, 6.19. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$: C, 67.74; H 6.45%).

On oxidation of the tetramethyl derivative with neutral permanganate solution, β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether (m.p. 109°) was obtained (mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether).

(α -*γ*-Dimethyl)- α -*γ*-bis-2,4-dihydroxybenzoylpropane (II: R=Me; R'=H).—Resorpiophenone⁴ was condensed in the usual way with methylene iodide and the product, isolated as in the previous case, was crystallised from ethanol in stout rods, m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 66.07; H, 5.90. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 66.27; H, 5.81%).

Infrared spectra (Fig. 1) of the above compound in nujol show λ_{max} at 3025, 1625, 1495, 1295, 1220, 1180, 1115, 1075, 1040, 990, 890, 825, 810, 790 cm^{-1} .

FIG. 1

1. Tetra-acetyl derivative of II (R=R'=H) (---)
2. Compound II (R=Me; R'=H) (—)
3. Compound II (R=Et; R'=H) (-.-.-)

²The authors are indebted to Dr W. Simon (Laboratorium für Organische Chemie Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule, Zürich) for mass spectrography.

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative crystallised from ethanol in cubic crystals, m.p. 203°. (Found: C, 63.0; H, 5.8. $C_{27}H_{28}O_{10}$ requires C, 63.28; H, 5.4%).

($\alpha\gamma$ -*Diethyl*)- $\alpha\gamma$ -*bis*-2,4-*dihydroxybenzoylpropane* (II): (R=Et; R'=H).—Resbutyrophenone⁴ condensed with methylene iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide and the product was crystallised from ethanol in rods, m.p. 138°. (Found: C, 67.9; H, 6.8. $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 67.7; H, 6.5%).

Infrared spectra (Fig. 1) of the above compound in nujol show λ_{max} at 3030, 1600, 1490, 1205, 1160, 1085, 1040, 985, 885, 860, 815, 745 cm^{-1} .

The *tetra-acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute ethanol in cubic crystals, m.p. 133°.

2,4-*DNP* crystallised from benzene-ethyl acetate, m.p. 238°. (Found: N, 14.91. $C_{33}H_{32}O_{12}N_8$ requires N, 15.3%).

$\alpha\gamma$ -*Bis*-2,4-*dihydroxy-5-chlorobenzoylpropane* (II:R=H; R'=Cl).—5-Chlororesacetophenone⁵ was condensed with methylene iodide as usual in presence of sodium ethoxide. The product crystallised from glacial acetic acid in stout needles, m.p. 284°. (Found C, 52.8; H, 3.8. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6Cl_2$ requires C, 53.0; H, 3.66%).

The 2,4-*DNP* crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 290° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.65. $C_{29}H_{22}O_{12}N_8Cl_2$ requires N, 15.0%).

($\alpha\gamma$ -*Dimethyl*)- $\alpha\gamma$ -*bis*-2,4-*dihydroxy-5-chlorobenzoylpropane* (II:R=Me; R'=Cl).—5-Chlororespropiofenone⁶ (5 g.) condensed with methylene iodide (6.7 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide (1.7 g. Na and 20 ml absolute EtOH). The reaction product, isolated in the usual way, crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles, m.p. 250°. (Found: C, 55.20; H, 4.20. $C_{19}H_{18}O_6Cl_2$ requires C, 55.20; H, 4.35%).

The 2,4-*DNP* crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 248°. (Found: N, 14.1. $C_{31}H_{26}O_{12}N_8Cl_2$ requires N, 14.48%).

5-*Chlororesbutyrophenone* (I:R=Et; R'=Cl.—A mixture of 4-chlororesorcin (12.5 g.), fused zinc chloride (12.5 g.), and butyric acid (12.5 g.) was heated for 3 minutes on a sand bath (140-15°). The dark brown viscous product was allowed to cool slowly for about an hour and then poured into an acidified (HCl) mixture of ice and water. The dark brown oil solidified on long standing and the product crystallised from dilute ethanol in cubes, m.p. 96°. (Found: C, 55.71; H, 5.4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires C, 55.94; H, 5.13%).

The 2,4-*DNP* melted at 235° (EtOH). (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{16}H_{15}O_6N_4Cl$ requires N, 14.2%).

The above ketone could not be condensed with methylene iodide in sodium ethoxide solution.

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4. Brewster and Hariris, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 52, 4868.

5. Chakravarti and Chakravarty, *this Journal*, 1939, 16, 144.